
Annotated Bibliography of the History and Culture of Eastern Turkistan, Jungharia/Zungaria/Dzungaria, Chinese Central Asia, and Sinkiang/Xinjiang (for the 16th-20th centuries CE, excluding most travel narratives)

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Introduction

The study of Eastern Turkistan or Xinjiang has long been hampered by geographic, cultural and linguistic complexity and difficult access to publications, but over the past 500 years, an enormous range of documentary materials have accumulated. Many Europeans have explored and studied the region since 1850 but their publications are often appear only in major research libraries and special collections, and even the travel accounts rarely reach a wider audience. Eastern Turkistan's scholarly and strategic importance has resulted in extensive publications in European and East Asian languages, particularly Russian, German, French, English, Chinese and Japanese. In addition, authors from the region and from other parts of the Islamic world have written literary, historiographic and religious works in Arabic, Persian and Turki, while Chinese travelers and colonial officials have also left extensive descriptions, particularly since the Manchu-Qing conquest in 1758 CE.

As a part of the "Silk Road," this region has been the conduit for people, culture and commerce since before recorded history. Much of the region's fame has arisen from the extensive archeological and documentary finds in the arid southern and eastern Xinjiang regions as well as nearby Dunhuang in Gansu, but Xinjiang's populated oases

and steppe continue to sustain its role as a region through which travelers and traders link East, Central and South Asian spiritual, literary and material cultures. Before the name Xinjiang was applied in 1884, the Chinese described it as Xiyu ("Western Regions") or Huijiang ("Muslim territories") while Central Asians called it Kashgaria, Altishahr or Yettishahr (6 or 7 cities) or Eastern Turkistan. All of these names have acquired political meanings in the present, with the Chinese government strongly attacking the term Eastern Turkistan as a sign of separatist and even terrorist leanings. The widespread Chinese concern about this term can be seen from a search at Google.com: using Chinese characters for *Dongtu* ("Eastern Turkistan") gives over one million hits, more than for either of the Chinese terms used for the Silk Road (*Sizhouzhilu* or *Silu*) and not far behind the 1.7 million hits for the name *Xinjiang* itself.

My goal in this bibliography is to introduce the study of the region through a classified list of the basic materials for study of culture and history over the past 500 years. The "Silk Road" is often described as in decline during this period, but in fact more recent Islamic and Mongol history is every bit as culturally rich and diverse as the preceding period, although the sources have not been as widely accessible to Western scholars. In compiling the present bibliography I found works

remaining difficult to access: items such as publications by Pantusov from 1880-1910 are only slightly more available in research library collections than more recent publications from Xinjiang. Useful material exists in dissertations, obscure serial publications or unpublished conference papers. Not very different from the latter are the many rare manuscripts held in collections around the world, which fortunately are now slowly being edited and published, although with less fanfare than the Dunhuang and Tarim region texts from earlier periods. As these become more accessible these materials will considerably deepen our understanding of the history and culture of Eastern Turkistan: similar results can be seen arising from recent use of Manchu language sources for the study of Qing China and Turkic and Persian sources for Central Asia. This bibliography should improve access and help guide future library cataloging of items in Central Asian languages.

Outline of Contents

I) Online Databases and Information Sources (all periods)

II) Selected Historical Background to 1500 CE and Regional Reference Works

III) Collected Works

IV) Serial publications

V) Bibliographies and Manuscript Descriptions

VI) Historical and Hagiographical Primary Sources

VII) Studies of History

VIII) World History, International Relations and Manchu-Junghar Interactions

IX) Western Explorers, Missionaries, and Consuls (excluding travel accounts not related to formal expeditions)

X) Basic Sources for Linguistics and Language Study

XI) Studies of Literature and Literary History

XII) Performing Arts, Ethnomusicology, Folklore, Folk Art, Architecture and Material Culture

XIII) Anthropology, Cultural Analysis, Ethnography, Ethnicity, Ethnogenesis

XIV) Religion: Islam, Khwâja Rule, Sufism, Shamanism

XV) Ecology, Economics, Geography, Pastoralism

XVI) Analyses of Social Policies, Politics, Strategic Issues and Current Events

I) Online Databases and Information Sources (all periods)

The following are the most comprehensive online sources for material on Xinjiang. My own bibliography is simply a list of the contents of the first 12 years of two important scholarly series in Xinjiang. The ODIAS and RIFIAS are likewise bibliographic sources. The Tôyô Bunko archive, IDP, ORIAS and Silk Road Seattle sites provide a wide range of important and hard-to-find materials directly online.

Bibliography of Uyghur language articles on history and literature by Nathan Light (lists contents of the series *Shinjang Tarikh Materiyyalliri* (volumes 1-33, 1980-1992) and the journal *Bulaq; Uyghur kilassik ädibiyati mäjmua'si* (issues 1-41, 1980-1992). *Bulaq* consists of editions and analyses of works of Eastern Turki (Uyghur) literature and translations of works from Persian

and Turkic languages. Most of these entries have also been entered into the ODIAS database.) <<http://homepages.utoledo.edu/nlight/uygarticles.htm>>.

Digital Archive of Tôyô Bunko Rare Books (35 books, 9062 pages from art historical and research publications from the past 150 years; high quality photos) <<http://dsr.nii.ac.jp/toyobunko/>>.

IDP: International Dunhuang Project Database (Search from collections of texts and artifacts from sites throughout Chinese Central Asia by Manuscript, Photograph, Artifact, Catalogue, Painting, and geographically by Map.) <<http://idp.bl.uk/ManuscriptSearch>>.

ODIAS (Online Databases for Inner Asia Studies, with citations for articles, books and manuscripts) <<http://www.gicas.jp/orias/odias.htm>>.

ORIAS Digitized books (Kashgar imprints from the Swedish Mission Press and Publications of China Inland Mission) <<http://www.gicas.jp/orias/digibooks.htm>>.

RIFIAS: Research Institute for Inner Asian Studies Online Library Catalog (A searchable library catalog of roughly 10,000 items available in the RIFIAS collection at Indiana University, Bloomington, along with a catalog of 400 RIFIAS publications.) <http://www.indiana.edu/~rifias/Library_Catalog.htm>.

Silk Road Seattle (research resources maintained under direction of Daniel C. Waugh) <<http://depts.washington.edu/uwch/silkroad/>>.

The Silk Road and Central Asia On the World Wide Web (links maintained by Daniel C. Waugh) <<http://depts.washington.edu/reecas/outreach/silklink.htm>>.

II) Selected Historical Background and Reference for Central Eurasia and Prior to 1500 CE

These are the most important works for an overview understanding the region and for guiding further research.

Bartold, V. V. *Turkestan Down to the Mongol Invasion*. 3rd ed. H.A.R. Gibb and Tatiana Minorsky, trans. C.E. Bosworth, ed. London, Luzac & co., 1968. [Online at the ACLS history e-book project: <<http://name.umdl.umich.edu/HEB00858.>>]

Beckwith, Christopher. *The Tibetan Empire in Central Asia: A history of the struggle for great power among Tibetans, Turks, Arabs, and Chinese during the Early Middle Ages*. Princeton: Princeton University Press, 1987.

Bregel, Yuri. *An Historical Atlas of Central Asia*. Leiden: E.J. Brill, 2003.

Chavannes, Édouard. *Documents sur Les Tou-Kiue (Turcs) occidentaux, recueillis et commentés, suivi de notes additionnelles*. Paris: Librairie d'Amérique et d'Orient, 1903.

Clark, Larry. "Introduction to the Uyghur Civil Documents of East Turkestan (13th-14th Centuries)." Unpublished Ph.D. dissertation. Indiana University, 1975.

Di Cosmo, Nicola, ed. *Warfare in Inner Asian History: 500-1800*. Leiden: Brill, 2002.

—. *Ancient China and its Enemies: The Rise of Nomadic Power in East Asian History*. New York: Cambridge University Press, 2002.

Eberhard, Wolfram. *China und seine westlichen Nachbarn: Beitrag zur mittelalterlichen und neueren Geschichte Zentralasiens*. Darmstadt: Wissenschaftliche Buchgesellschaft, 1978.

Elverskog, Johan. *Uyghur Buddhist literature*. Turnhout: Brepols, 1997.

Golden, Peter. *An Introduction to the History of the Turkic Peoples*. Wiesbaden: Otto Harrassowitz, 1992.

Güzel, Hasan Celal, et al, eds. *The Turks*. 6 vols. Ankara: Yeni Türkiye, 2002. [Chronological collection of articles of varying scholarly depth and accuracy. First 3 volumes include articles on Central Asian Turkic peoples.]

Hamilton, James Russell. *Les Ouïghours à l'époque des Cinq Dynasties d'après les documents chinois*. Paris, 1955.

- History of Civilizations of Central Asia*. Paris: Unesco, 1992-. 5 vols. [An extensive publishing project including over 100 articles on culture, history, religions, society and technology of the region. Some of this material is online at <http://www.unesco.org/culture/asia/html_eng/ouvrages.htm>.]
- Han, Xiang. *Qiuci shi ku*. Ürümchi: Xinjiang Daxue chubanshe, 1990. [Extensive discussion of the Qiuci caves near Kucha, with many color plates.]
- Hung, Chin-Fu. "China and The Nomads: Misconceptions in Western Historiography on Inner Asia." *Harvard Journal of Asiatic Studies*, 41/2 (1981): 597-628. [Critical review of Luc Kwanten's history *Imperial Nomads*.]
- Ji Dachun, ed. *Xinjiang lishi cidian*. Ürümchi: Xinjiang renmin chubanshe, 1993. [Dictionary of Xinjiang history.]
- Kamberi, Dolkun. "A survey of Uyghur documents from Turpan and their importance for Asian and central Eurasian history." *Central Asian Survey*, 18/3 (1999): 281-301.
- Komaroff, Linda and Stefano Carboni. *The legacy of Genghis Khan: courtly art and culture in western Asia, 1256-1353*. New York: Metropolitan Museum of Art, 2002. [Online selections in nicely-designed exhibit at: <http://www.lacma.org/khan/index_flash.htm>.]
- Laut, Jens Peter. *Der frühe türkische Buddhismus und seine literarischen Denkmäler*. (Veröffentlichungen der Societas Uralo-Altica, vol. 21). Wiesbaden: Otto Harrassowitz, 1986.
- Lieu, Samuel N. C. *Manichaeism in Central Asia and China*. Leiden: Brill, 1998.
- Lin Enxian. *Tujue yanjiu*. [Turk studies.] Taipei: Taiwan shangwu yingshuguan, 77 [1988].
- Liu, Mau-Ts'ai. *Die chinesischen Nachrichten zur Geschichte der Ost-Türken (T'u-Küe)*. 2 vols. Asiatische Forschungen, 10. Wiesbaden: Otto Harrassowitz, 1958.
- . *Kutscha und seine Beziehungen zu China von 2. Jh. v. bis zum 6. Jh. n. Chr.*, 2 vols. Asiatische Forschungen, 27. Wiesbaden: Otto Harrassowitz, 1969.
- Liu Weixin, ed. *Xibei minzu cidian*. Ürümchi: Xinjiang renmin chubanshe, 1998. [Dictionary of N.W. nationalities.]
- Mackerras, Colin P. *The Uighur Empire according to the T'ang Dynastic Histories: A Study in Sino-Uighur Relations 744-840*. Canberra: Australian National University Press, 1972. [Online publication of one of the two primary source texts in this book, at: <<http://depts.washington.edu/uwch/silkroad/texts/tangshu/tangshu.html>>.]
- Mair, Victor, ed. *The Bronze Age and Early Iron Age Peoples of Eastern Central Asia*. 2 vols. Philadelphia: Institute for the Study of Man, 1998.
- Mallory, J. P. and Victor H. Mair. *The Tarim Mummies, Ancient China and the Mystery of the Earliest Peoples from the West*. London: Thames & Hudson, 2000.
- Mei Jianjun. *Copper and Bronze Metallurgy in Late Prehistoric Xinjiang: Its Cultural Context and Relationship with Neighboring Regions*. BAR International Series 865. Oxford: Archaeopress, 2000.
- Rhie, Marylin M. *Early Buddhist Art of China and Central Asia*. 2 vols. in 3. Handbuch der Orientalistik. Leiden: Brill, 1999.
- Rossabi, Morris, ed. *China among Equals: The Middle Kingdom and its Neighbors, 10th-14th Centuries*. Berkeley: University of California Press, 1983.
- Roxburgh, David J. *Turks: A Journey of a Thousand Years, 600-1600*. London: Royal Academy Books, 2005.
- Thomas, Frederick William. *Tibetan literary texts and documents concerning Chinese Turkestan*. 4 vols. London: The Royal Asiatic Society, 1935-1965
- Whitfield, Susan and Ursula Sims-Williams, eds. *The Silk Road: trade, travel, war and faith*. London: British Library, 2004.
- Yarshater, Ehsan, ed. *Encyclopædia Iranica*. London: Routledge & Kegan Paul, 1985-. [Also online at: <<http://www.iranica.com/articlenavigation/index.html>>.]
- Zieme, Peter. *Die Stabreimtexte der Uiguren von Turfan und Dunhuang. Studien zur alttürkischen Dichtung*. Bibliotheca Orientalis Hungarica, 33. Budapest: Akadémiai Kiadó, 1991.

III) Collected Works

The collections below represent significant research compilations. A number of volumes of articles in Russian and many in Chinese are also valuable but less accessible. The Starr and CEMOTI volumes are both primarily oriented towards analysis of international relations, development, politics and statistics rather than ethnographic study. The Benson and Svanberg volume is somewhat more concerned with cultural analysis.

Benson, Linda, and Ingvar Svanberg, eds. *The Kazaks of China: essays on an ethnic minority*. Stockholm: Almqvist & Wiksell, 1988. Contents:

L. Benson and I. Svanberg. "The Kazakhs in Xinjiang."

Ingvar Svanberg. "The Nomadism of Orta •üz Kazaks in Xinjiang, 1911-1949."

L. Benson. "Osman Batur: The Kazak's Golden Legend."

Mark Kirchner. "The Language of the Kazaks from Xinjiang: A Text Sample."

Thomas Hoppe. "Kazak Pastoralism in the Bogda Range."

Cahiers d'études sur la Méditerranée orientale et le monde turco-iranien (CEMOTI) 25: Les Ouïgours au vingtième siècle (1998).

Françoise Aubin. "L'arrière-plan historique du nationalisme ouïgour. Le Turkestan oriental des origines au XXème siècle."

Dru C. Gladney. "Internal Colonialism and the Uyghur Nationality: Chinese Nationalism and Its Subaltern Subjects."

Michel Jan. "L'intégration du Xinjiang dans l'ensemble chinois: vulnérabilité et sécurité."

Artoush Kumul. "Témoignage - Le "séparatisme" ouïgour au

XXème siècle: histoire et actualité."

Ildiko Beller-Hann. "Work and Gender among Uighur Villagers in Southern Xinjiang."

Gülzade Tanridagli. "Le roman historique, véhicule du nationalisme ouïgour."

Cheripjan Nadirov. "La structure économique de la région autonome du Xinjiang ouïgour et sa place dans le système des relations sino-kazakhes."

Hamide Khamraev. "La géopolitique du pétrole."

Hegel Ishakov et Khadia Akhmedova. "Les migrations des Ouïgours vers l'Asie centrale ex-soviétique."

Frédérique-Jeanne Besson. "Les Ouïgours hors du Turkestan oriental: de l'exil à la formation d'une diaspora."

Starr, S. Frederick, ed. *Xinjiang: China's Muslim Borderland*. Armonk, N.Y.: M.E. Sharpe, 2004.

James A. Millward, Peter C. Perdue. "Political and Cultural History of the Xinjiang Region through the Late Nineteenth Century."

James A. Millward, Nabijan Tursun. "Political History and Strategies of Control, 1884-1978."

Dru C. Gladney. "The Chinese Program of Development and Control, 1978-2001."

Yitzhak Shichor. "The Great Wall of Steel: Military and Strategy in Xinjiang."

Calla Wiemer. "The Economy of Xinjiang."

Linda Benson. "Education and Social Mobility among Minority Populations in Xinjiang."

Sean R. Roberts. "A 'Land of Borderlands': Implications of Xinjiang's Trans-border Interactions."

Stanley W. Toops. "The Demography of Xinjiang" and "The Ecology of Xinjiang: A Focus on Water."

Jay Dautcher. "Public Health and Social Pathologies in Xinjiang."

Justin Rudelson, William Jankowiak. "Acculturation and Resistance: Xinjiang Identities in Flux."

Graham E. Fuller, Jonathan N. Lipman. "Islam in Xinjiang."

Gardner Bovington, Nabijan Tursun. "Contested Histories."

Dru C. Gladney. "Responses to Chinese Rule: Patterns of Cooperation and Opposition."

16-page "Bibliographic Guide to Xinjiang."

IV) Serial publications

The following are the more important serials and periodicals devoted to the history and culture of Xinjiang published in China and suggest the immense range of new publishing that began in the 1980s. I have not listed most popularly-oriented publications, nor those that primarily express Chinese government or local and émigré dissident political perspectives.

Bulaq; Uyghur kilassik ädibiyati mäjmu'äsi. [Bulaq: Journal of Uyghur classical literature.] Ürümchi, 1980-. [Has published around 20,000 pages of articles and literary editions since inception.]

Miras; päsilik zhurnal. [Heritage; quarterly journal. Published by the Junggo khälq eghiz ädibiyat-sän'ät tätqiqat jämiyiti Shinjang Uyghur aptonom rayonluq shöbisi; Uyghur tätqiqat ishkhanişi.] Ürümchi, 1983-. [Popularly-oriented journal about Uyghur literature, folklore, and folk art.]

Shinjang Dashösi ilmiy zhurnili. Pälsäpä-ijtima'i pän qismi. [Xinjiang University Scientific Journal. Philosophy and Social Science Section.] Ürümchi, 1980-.

Shinjang ijtimai' panlar tatqiqati. Xinjiang shehui kexueyuan xuebao. [Journal of the Xinjiang Academy of Social Sciences.] Ürümchi, 1981-.

Shinjang mädäniyät; qosh ayliq universal ädäbiy zhurnal. [Xinjiang civilization; bi-monthly journal of universal literature. Popular journal with articles and literature by Uyghurs, apparently began publishing in Ürümchi in 1951.]

Shinjang Qirghiz adabiyati = Xinjiang Kirghiz literature. Ürümchi, 1981-.

Shinjang tarikh materiyalliri. [Xinjiang historical materials.] 1980-. [Irregular volumes of articles most

of which also appear in Chinese versions in the series *Xinjiang wenshi ziliao xuanji*.]

Shinjang täzkirisi [Xinjiang annals]. 1983-. [Local histories are now also published in the multi-volume *Shinjang omumii täzkirisi*, beginning in 1996.]

Shinjang Tibbiy Instituti ilmii zhurnili = Xinjiang yixueyuan xuebao = Acta Academiae Medicinae Xinjiang. Ürümchi, 1985-.

Tängritagh; qosh ayliq ädibiy zhurnal [Tangritagh; bi-monthly literary journal.] 1980s-. [Popular literary magazine published in Ürümchi.]

Tarim; ayliq ädäbiy zhurnal. [Tarim; monthly literary journal.] 1950-. [Contemporary literary compositions, translations and commentary.]

Uyghur khälq chöchäkliri. Ürümchi, 1979-. [At least 11 irregular volumes of folk tales.]

Uyghur khälq dastanliri. Ürümchi, 1981-. [At least 4 volumes of *dastan* prose and poetry narratives.]

Uyghur khälq nakhshiliri. Ürümchi, 1980-. At least 6 volumes of folk songs with musical transcriptions.]

Uyghur khälq qoshaqliri. Ürümchi, 1979-. [Folk quatrains with musical transcriptions.]

Xibei minzu yanjiu = Research in N.W. national minorities. [Academic journal published in Lanzhou.]

Xiyu yanjiu = The Western Regions Studies. Ürümchi, 1991-.

Zhongguo bianjiang shidi yanjiu; China's borderland history and geography studies. Beijing, 1991-. [Another recently established journal.]

V) Bibliographies and Manuscript Descriptions

The most important primary sources for study of the past 500 years are Persian, Turkic, Manchu and Chinese manuscript and archival documents. The extensive Chinese sources have appeared in a number of facsimile editions and I list only a few of the research guides to them here. The other sources are only beginning to be systematically studied and published and

access remains a problem. Although most have some deficiencies, the sources below are the best descriptions of the available primary and secondary source materials.

Abdurahman, Amina and Jin Yu-Ping. "Une vue d'ensemble des manuscrits tchagatay du Xinjiang." In: *La Mémoire et ses supports en Asie Centrale*. Les Cahiers d'Asie centrale N°8. Vincent Fourniau, ed. Aix-en-Provence: Institut Français d'Etude sur l'Asie Centrale, 2000, pp. 35-62.

Bregel, Yuri. *Bibliography of Islamic Central Asia*. 3 vols. Bloomington, Indiana: Research Institute for Inner Asian Studies, Indiana University, 1995. [Classified bibliography of 30,500 books and articles on the history and culture of Central Asia (including Chinese Central Asia) published from the 17th century through 1988. All languages except East Asian.]

Chen Yanqi and Sasha. *Xiyu yanjiu shumu*. Ürümqi: Xinjiang renmin chubanshe, 1990. [Classified bibliography of 6734 Chinese, European, Russian and Japanese books on Central Asia and Xinjiang (known in Chinese as *Xiyu* or the Western Regions).]

Hamada Masami. "Research Trends in Xinjiang Studies." In *Research Trends in Modern Central Eurasian Studies (18th-20th Centuries)*: A Selective and Critical Bibliography of Works Published between 1985 and 2000. Part 1. Stéphane A. Dudoignon and Komatsu Hisao, eds. Tokyo: The Toyo Bunko, 2003.

Hartmann, Martin. "Die osttürkischen Handschriften der Sammlung Hartmann." *Mitteilungen des Seminars für Orientalische Sprachen*, 7 (1904): 1-21.

Hofman, H. F. *Turkish literature. A bio-bibliographical survey*. Section III. *Muslim Central Asian Turkish literature*. 6 volumes bound as 2. Utrecht: Royal Asiatic Society of Great Britain and Ireland, 1969. [Erudite, chatty and often obscure annotations on the authors and works of Central Asian Turkic manuscript literature.]

Hoppe, Thomas. *Xinjiang-Arbeitsbibliographie II: Autonomes*

Gebiet Xinjiang der Uiguren, China (Naturbedingungen, Geschichte, Ethnien, Landnutzung); Xinjiang provisional bibliography II: Xinjiang Uigur Autonomous Region, China (natural conditions, history, ethnic groups, land use). Wiesbaden: O. Harrassowitz, 1987. [Roughly 2000 items primarily in English, German, Russian, Chinese and Uyghur.]

Kaidarov, A. *Uigurskii iazyk i literatura. Annotirovannyy bibliograficheskii ukazatel'*. [Uyghur Language and Literature. Bibliographic Index.] Tom 1. Alma-Ata: AN Kazakhskoi SSR, 1962.

Lin Enxian. *Jindai Zhongguo bianjiang yanjiu lunzhu mulu*. Taipei: National Chengchi University, Institute of China Border Area Studies, 75 [1986].

Liu Ge and Huang Xianyang. *Xiyu shidi lunwen cailiao suoyin*. Ürümqi: Xinjiang renmin chubanshe, 1988. [Classified bibliography of 8032 articles in Chinese about history, minorities, economy, culture, literature, language, geography and archeology of the "Western Regions."]

Matsuura, S. "A bibliography of works on the Manchu and Sibo languages." *Memoirs of the Research Department of the Tôyô Bunko* 38 (1980), p. 95-179. [Sibo or Xibe is the only form of Manchu that continues to be spoken and written in China.]

Muginov, Abdulladzhon Muginovich. *Opisanie uigurskikh rukopisei Instituta Narodov Azii*. [Description of Uyghur Manuscripts in the Institute of the Peoples of Asia.] Moscow: 1962. [Classifies a group of traditional manuscripts as "Uyghur" based on linguistic features, and time and place of composition, while ignoring other popular Turkic and Persian works found in Eastern Turkistan.]

Sawut, Torsunmuhämmät. *Uyghur ädäbiyati tarikhi materiyallar katalogi*. Ürümqi: Shinjang Dashö Därslik Bölümü, 1991. [A typescript volume listing 3541 books and articles about Uyghur literary history, organized by period and subject, and 665 manuscript titles held in eight collections in Ürümqi.]

Shinjang Uyghur Aptonom Rayonluq Az Sanliq Millät Qädimki Äsärlerini

Toplash, Rätläsh, Näshir Qilishni Pilanlash Rähbärlük Guruppa Ishkhanisi. *Uyghur, Özbek, Tatar Qädimki äsärklär tizimlikli*. Qäshqär: Qäshqär Uyghur Näshriyatı, 1988. [A catalogue of approximately 1500 Turkic, Persian and Arabic manuscripts and lithographs held in the Xinjiang libraries. All from the Islamic period and in Arabic script.]

Sary, Giovanni. *Manchu Studies. An International Bibliography*. 3 vols. Wiesbaden: Harrassowitz, 1990.

Umemura Hiroshi. *Japanese studies on Inner Asian history, 1973-1983*. Tokyo: Centre for East Asian Cultural Studies, 1987. [Bibliography in Japanese and English; introductory article in English.]

Yuan Tongli. *Shinkyô kenkyû bunken mokuroku, 1886-1962: Nichibunbon = Classified bibliography of Japanese books and articles concerning Sinkiang, 1886-1962*. Tokyo: Shoei-Insatsu Co., 1962.

Zhongguo weiwuer lishi wenhua yanjiuhui. *Weiwuer lishi wenhua yanjiu wenxian tilu*. Beijing: Minzu chubanshe, 2000. [Geng Shimin (<http://www.eurasianhistoryf.com/en/en_lunwen/20041210063002.htm>) cites this as a bibliography of 6980 entries on Uyghur history and culture but I find no other citation for this item.]

VI) Historical and Hagiographical Primary Sources

The following are the few editions and translations that have made local primary source documents and compositions available. These editions are of widely varying quality. I again avoid most of the Chinese local histories and gazeteers although these have been heavily used by Enoki, Fletcher, Hamada, Kim, Millward, and Saguchi. Kim's endnotes are a comprehensive discussion on the different sources for 19th century history.

Alptekin, Isa Yusuf and M. Ali Tasçi. *Esir Dogu Türkistan için: Isa Yusuf Alptekin'in mücadele hatıraları*. Istanbul: Dogu Türkistan Nesriyat Merkezi, 1985. [Edited memoirs of an important East Turkistani leader.]

Baldick, Julian. *Imaginary Muslims*. London: Routledge, 1993. [A

translation and epitome of a key hagiographic source for Eastern Turkistan. For details about the work and problems with this translation, see DeWeese, "The *Tadhkira-i Bughra-khan*..."

Chinggiznamä. Haji Nurhaji, ed. Kashgar: Qäshqär Uyghur Näshriyati, 1985. [Edited from a manuscript now held at the Xinjiang Academy of Social Sciences, #00679. Matches the anonymous *Târikh-i Kâshgar* (see below) but here ascribed to Molla Mersalih Kashqäri.]

Churâs, Shâh Mahmûd ibn Mirza Fazil. *Khronika*. Text, translation, notes, indices by O. F. Akimushkin. Moscow: Nauka, 1976. [Churâs wrote this Persian history, simply called *Târikh*, in Kashgar in the seventeenth century, describing the cultural life and history of the court and its military encounters. It is composed as a continuation of the work of Mîrzâ Haydar.]

DeWeese, Devin. "The *Tadhkira-i Bughra-khan* and the 'Uvaysi' Sufis of Central Asia: Notes in Review of *Imaginary Muslims*." *Central Asiatic Journal* 40:1 (1996): 87-127.

Di Cosmo, Nicola and Dalizhabu Bao. *Manchu-Mongol relations on the eve of the Qing conquest: a documentary history*. Leiden: Brill, 2003.

Gürsoy-Naskali, Emine, transl. and ed. *Ashâbu'l-Kahf; A treatise in Eastern Turki*. Helsinki: Suomalais-ugrilainen seura, 1985. [Valuable study of a tomb and pilgrimage site near Turfan where the story of the Seven Sleepers of Ephesus has become locally attached. Qurbân'ali Khâlidî (see below) describes traveling to this site in his *Târikh-i jarîda-yi jadîda*.]

Imbault-Huart, Camille. *Recueil de documents sur l'Asie centrale*. Paris: Leroux, 1881. [Translations from Chinese sources on 19th century rebellions in Eastern Turkistan.]

—. *Le pays de Hami ou Khamil; description, histoire d'après les auteurs chinois*, Paris, E. Leroux, 1892.

Mîrzâ Haydar. *A history of the Moghuls of central Asia; being the Tarikh-i-Rashidi of Mirza Muhammad*

Haidar, Dughlat. Edited, with commentary, notes, and map by N. Elias, translated by E. Denison Ross. London: Curzon, 1898. [Excerpts are available online at: <<http://depts.washington.edu/uwch/silkroad/texts/rash1.html>>.]

—. *Mirza Haydar Dughlat's Tarikh-i-Rashidi: a history of the khans of Moghulistan*. English translation & annotation by W.M. Thackston. Cambridge: Harvard University, Dept. of Near Eastern Languages and Civilizations, 1996.

—. *Târikh-i Rashîdî: târikh-i khavânîn-i Mughûlistân; matn-i Fârsî*. Cambridge: Dänishgâh-i Hârvârd, 1996. [Text of the original Persian version of the *Târikh-i Rashîdî*.]

Molla Haji. *Boghrakhanlar täzkirisî*. Abdurehim Sabit, ed. Qäshqär: Qäshqär Uyghur Näshriyati, 1988. [Prepared from a 19th century manuscript in the complex body of hagiographical histories around Satuq Boghra Khan. See Baldick *Imaginary Muslims* and DeWeese, "The *Tadhkira-i Bughra-khan*..." for more information.]

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VII) Studies of History

The more important historical studies, using Chinese, Turkic, and Persian sources as well as the archival documents of the British, Ottoman, Russian and Qing Empires. Some Soviet-era studies exhibit anti-Chinese biases, although B.A. Akhmedov and Iu. G. Baranova are free of these. The works of Benson, Forbes, Kim, Saguchi, and Wang are generally excellent, although Baranova already put forth Kim's argument about Ya'qûb Beg's international balancing act. The works of Bughra, Kurban, Saray, Turfani, Aitchen Wu and Sheng Shi-tsai (with Whiting) exhibit the biases of political participants and their allies.

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VIII) World History, International Relations and Manchu-Junghar Interactions

Originating in the work of Paul Pelliot, Owen Lattimore and especially Joseph Fletcher, interest in world historical approaches to the study of Chinese Central Asia and adjoining regions has been expanding. Obviously relevant

are the political interactions of Mongol states with their neighbors. Among these the Moghuls and Oyirad/Junghar/Kalmyk Mongols were among the last to maintain Chingizid principles of legitimation. Another important and heavily studied international dimension involves Ya'qûb Beg's struggles to maintain power through alliances with the Qing, Russian, British and even Ottoman empires. The scholars making the best use of available archives and materials include Di Cosmo, Fletcher, Millward, Miyawaki, Moiseev, Pelliot, Perdue, and Zlatkin.

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IX) Western Explorers, Missionaries, and Consuls (excluding travel accounts not related to formal expeditions)

The works listed below are the more important accounts of ethnographic and archaeological expeditions in Eastern Turkistan since the mid-1800s. Most of these expeditions also result in extensive publications about archaeological and manuscript materials. I have left out many publications by Japanese and Russian explorers because these are readily found through the secondary sources listed here. There are also at least 400 travel narratives in Western languages and many more in Chinese and Japanese. Daniel Waugh and Adela Lee's compilation of bibliographies on early travelers on the Silk Road has made an excellent beginning for the ancient and medieval periods (<<http://www.silk-road.com/artl/srtravelmain.shtml>>) and will be supplemented soon.

Many briefer accounts from travelers and explorers appear in journals. Most of the English-language journals are available in the JSTOR database of journal page images beginning in the late 1800s. The breadth of coverage (and variety of spellings and names) in the journals at JSTOR.org can be seen from the following statistics on searches using geographic terms: 1583 for *Sinkiang*, 873 for *Xinjiang* and 51 for *Hsin-chiang*; 942 for *Chinese Turkestan* and 366 for *Eastern Turkestan* (using *Turkistan* in each phrase gives 400 more); 736 for *Khotan* and 38 for *Hotan*; 612 for *Yarkand*; 852 for *Kashgar* and 72 for *Kashghar*; 862 for *Turfan* and 18 for *Turpan*; 425 for *Hami* and 23 for *Qomul*; 174 for *Dzungaria* and 28 for *Zungaria*; 258 for *Urumchi* and 33 for *Tihwa*;

146 for *Kuldja* and 89 for *Kulja*; 49 for *Korla*; 52 for *Chuguchak*, 53 for *Tarbagatai* and 23 for *Tacheng*; etc.

Ambolt, Nils. *Karavan: Travels in Eastern Turkestan*. Foreword by Sven Hedin. Translated from the Swedish by Joan Bulman. London & Glasgow: Blackie and Son Limited, 1939.

Baud, A., Ph. Forêt and S. Gorshenina. *La Haute-Asie telle qu'ils l'ont vue. Explorateurs et scientifiques de 1820-1940*. Geneva: Editions Olizane, 2003.

Cable, Mildred and Francesca French. *George Hunter, Apostle of Turkestan*. London: China Inland Mission, 1948.

Clark, Milton J. "How the Kazakhs Flew to Freedom." *National Geographic Magazine*, 106/5 (1954): 621-644.

—. "Leadership and Political Allocation in Sinkiang Kazak Society." Unpublished Ph.D. Dissertation. Harvard University, 1955. [Unfortunately Harvard libraries make the unique copy of this work based on first-hand experience impossible to borrow.]

Dabbs, Jack Autrey. *History of the Discovery and Exploration of Chinese Turkestan*. The Hague, Mouton, 1963.

de Filippi, Filippo, Giotto Dainelli and John Alfred Spranger. *The Italian expedition to the Himalaya, Karakoram and Eastern Turkestan (1913-1914)*. London: E. Arnold & Co., 1932.

Forsyth, Thomas Douglas, et al. *Report of a mission to Yarkund in 1873*. Calcutta: Foreign Dept. Press, 1875.

Gorshenina, Svetlana. *Explorateurs en Asie Centrale: Voyageurs et aventuriers de Marco Polo à Ella Maillart*. Genève: Éditions Olizane, 2003. [Annotated bibliography of travel accounts.]

Grenard, Fernand. *J.-L. Dutreuil de Rhins; Mission scientifique dans la haute Asie, 1890-1895*. 2 vols. Paris: E. Leroux, 1897-1898. [This important description of exploration, history, folklore and religious

traditions was completed by Grenard after the death of Dutreuil de Rhins.]

Hedin, Sven. *Through Asia*. J. T. Bealby, trans. 2 vols. London: Methuen, 1899. [Account of expedition 1893-97.]

—. *Central Asia and Tibet*. J. T. Bealby, trans. 2 vols. London: Hurst and Blackett, 1903. [1899-1902 expedition to Chinese Turkistan and Tibet.]

—, et al. *Scientific Results of a Journey in Central Asia 1899-1902*. 6 vols. Stockholm: Lithographic Institute of the General staff of the Swedish army, 1904-1907.

—. *Riddles of the Gobi desert*. Elizabeth Sprigge and Claude Napier, trans. New York: E. P. Dutton, 1933.

—. *The Flight of "Big Horse"; the trail of war in Central Asia*. F. H. Lyon, trans. New York: E. P. Dutton, 1936.

—. *The Silk Road*. F. H. Lyon, trans. New York: E. P. Dutton, 1938.

—. *The Wandering Lake*. F. H. Lyon, trans. New York: E. P. Dutton, 1940. [Hedin's discovery of why the location of Lake Lop-Nor changed over the centuries.]

[For an introduction to Hedin's voluminous bibliography, see Daniel C. Waugh's "A Sven Hedin Bibliography" <<http://www.silkroadfoundation.org/bibliography/hedinb3.html>>.]

Hopkirk, Peter. *Foreign devils on the silk road: the search for the lost cities and treasures of Chinese Central Asia*. Amherst: University of Massachusetts Press, 1980.

Jarring, Gunnar. *Return to Kashgar: Central Asian memoirs in the present*. Durham: Duke University Press, 1986.

Kliashstorny, S. G., et al. *Vostochnyi Turkestan glazami Russkikh puteshestvennikov*. [East Turkistan through the Eyes of Russian Travelers.] Alma-Ata: "Nauka" Kazakhskoi SSR, 1988.

Lattimore, Owen. *High Tartary*. Boston: Little, Brown, 1930. [Travels through Northern Xinjiang in 1927.]

Le Coq, Albert von. *Buried treasures of Chinese Turkestan: an account of the activities and adventures of the*

second and third German Turfan expeditions. Anna Barwell, trans. London: G. Allen & Unwin, 1928.

—. *Von Land und Leuten in Ostturkistan: Berichte und Abenteuer der 4. deutschen Turfanexpedition*. Leipzig: J.C. Hinrichs, 1928.

Mannerheim, Carl Gustaf Emil. *Across Asia from West to East in 1906-1908*. 2 vols. Helsinki, 1940.

Michell, John. *The Russians in Central Asia ... descriptions of Chinese Turkestan and Dzungaria by Capt. Valikhanof, M. Veniukof, etc.* London: E. Stanford, 1865.

Mirsky, Jeannette. *Sir Aurel Stein, archaeological explorer*. Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 1977. [Largely a summary/precis of his writings.]

Obzor russkikh puteshestvii i ekspeditsii v Sredniuiu Aziyu. Materialy k istorii izucheniia Srednei Azii, 4 pts. O. V. Maslova, comp. Tashkent: Izd-vo "FAN" Uzbekskoi SSR, 1955-1971. [Valuable annotated bibliography of Russian travelers and expeditions in Central Asia from 1715-1886.]

Paxton, John Hall. *Papers*. Yale University Library, Manuscripts and Archives, Manuscript Group Number 629. [U.S. consul in Xinjiang 1945-1949. Author of "Escape over the Roof of the World" in the *Saturday Evening Post* and *U.S. Camera* photo essay on the escape (June 1951).]

Pevtsov, M. V. *Puteshestvie po Vostochnomu Turkestanu, Kun-Luniu, severnoi okraïne tibetskago nago'ia i Chzhungarii v 1889-m i 1890-m godakh*. [Journey through East Turkestan, the Kun-Lun and the Northern Fringes of the Tibetan Plateau and Jungharia in 1889 and 1890.] St. Petersburg: M. Stasiulevich, 1895. [Partial translation as "An Ethnographic Sketch of Kashgaria." *Journal of Steward Anthropological Society*, 12 (1982).]

Przheval'skii, Nikolai Mikhailovich. *From Kulja, across the Tian Shan to Lob-Nor*. E. Delmar Morgan, tr.; T. D. Forsyth, intro. London: S. Low, Marston, Searle, & Rivington, 1879.

Skrine, C. P. *Chinese Central Asia*. London,: Methuen, 1926. [Still

valuable descriptive account based on his travels in Western Xinjiang while British Consul in Kashgar, 1922-1924.]

Stein, M. Aurel. *Sand-buried ruins of Khotan; personal narrative of a journey of archaeological & geographical exploration in Chinese Turkestan*. London: T.F. Unwin, 1903.

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—. *Ruins of desert Cathay; personal narrative of explorations in Central Asia and westernmost China*. London: Macmillan and Co., 1912.

—. *Serindia: detailed report of explorations in Central Asia and westernmost China*. 5 vols. Oxford: Clarendon Press, 1921.

Walker, Annabel, *Aurel Stein: Pioneer of the Silk Road*. London: John Muray, 1995. [Serious biography based on Stein archive.]

Waugh, Daniel C. "The 'mysterious and terrible Karatash gorges': notes and documents on the explorations by Stein and Skrine." *Geographical Journal*, 165/3 (1999): 306-20.

Whitfield, Susan. *Aurel Stein on the Silk Road*. Serindia Publications, 2004. [Excellent, illustrated introduction to Stein for the general reader.]

X) Basic Sources for Linguistics and Language Study

Turkic, Manchu, and Mongol linguistics are vast fields and many works have been published on these and other historical and modern languages of Eastern Turkistan. The list below primarily references works useful for studying modern Uyghur since it is the dominant language of the region and has only a limited number of speakers elsewhere. The most comprehensive bilingual dictionaries are those produced by Nadzhip, Iliiev and Schwarz, while the multivolume dictionary produced by Abliz

Yaqub, et al, provides examples of usage. Schwarz and Jarring both include information about etymology and Schwarz provides classified word lists and illustrations. A comprehensive dialect dictionary has yet to be produced, but Ghopuri, Jarring, Malov, Osmanov, Sadvaqasov, and Tenishev have gathered important materials. Many of the collections of oral texts listed below consist are folklore materials.

Abikänuli, Nurbäk. *Qazaqsha-khanzusha sözdik* [Qazaq-Chinese Dictionary.] Beijing: Minzu chubanshe, 1989. [Extensive and accurate bilingual dictionary.]

Duval, Jean-R. "Modern Uyghur, A Historical Perspective." In: *Culture Contact, History and Ethnicity in Inner Asia*. Michael Gervers and Wayne Schlepp, eds. Toronto: Joint Center for Asia Pacific Studies, 1996, pp. 132-67.

Dwyer, Arienne. "Language Contact in Qumul." *Journal of Central Asian Studies*, 3/1 (Fall-Winter 1998): 30-41.

Ghopuri, Ghulam. *Uyghur shiviliri sözlügi*. Beijing: Millätlär Näshriyati, 1986.

—, Muhämmät Tursun Ibrahim, Khoja Äkhmät Yünüs, compilers. *Uyghur kilassik ädäbiyatidin qisqichä sözlük*. Beijing: Millätlär Näshriyati, 1986.

Hahn, Reinhard and Ablahat Ibrahim. *Spoken Uyghur*. Seattle: University of Washington Press, 1991. [An introductory text book.]

Iliiev, A., et al. *Russko-uygurskii slovar'*. Moscow: Gos. Izd-vo inostrannykh slovarei, 1956. [30,000 word Russian-Uyghur dictionary.]

Jarring, Gunnar. *An Eastern Turkic-English Dialect Dictionary*. *Lunds universitets årsskrift*. N.F. Avd. 1, bd. 56, nr. 4. Lund: C. W. K. Gleerup, 1964. [Roughly 15,000 entries.]

—. "The Toponym Takla-Makan." *Turkic Studies*, 1/2 (1997): 227-41.

Qawuz, Qadir. *Han-Ying-Wei chengyu cidian= A Chinese-English-*

Uighur dictionary of idioms = Khänzuchä-Inglizchä-Uyghurchä turaqliq ibarilär lughiti. Ürümchi: Shinjang Khälq Näshriyati, 1990. [Provides translations and explanations for roughly 10,600 proverbs and sayings.]

Malov, S. E. *Lobnorskii iazyk.* [The Lobnor Language.] Frunze: Izd-vo AN Kirgizskoi SSR, 1956.

— *Uigurskie narechiia Sin'tsziana: teksty, perevody, slovar'.* [The Uyghur Dialects of Xinjiang: Texts, Translations, Dictionary.] Moscow: Izd-vo vostochnoi lit-ry, 1961.

— *Uigurskii iazyk: khamiiskoe narechie: teksty, perevody i slovar'.* [The Uyghur Language: The Hami Dialect. Texts, Translations and Dictionary.] Moscow: Izd-vo AN SSSR, 1954.

— "Materialy po uigurskim narechiam Sin'tsziana." [Materials on the Uyghur Dialects of Xinjiang.] In: *Sergeiu Fedorovichu Ol'den-burgu: k piatidesiatiletiu nauchno-obshchestvennoi deiatel'nosti, 1882-1932.* Leningrad, 1934, pp. 307-322.

Mawkanuli, Talant. "The Jungar Tuvas: Language and National Identity in the PRC." *Central Asian Survey*, 20/4 (2001): 497-517.

Nadzhip, Emir N. *Uigursko-russkii slovar.* Moscow: "Sov. entsiklopediia," 1968. [Uyghur-Russian dictionary, with very detailed entries for roughly 33,000 words.]

Osmanov, Mirsultan, Ansardin Musa, and Osman Nadir. *Hazirqi zaman uyghur tili dialektliri.* Ürümchi: Shinjang Yashlar-ösmürlär näshriyati, 1990.

Päyzulla, Änwär. *Inglizchä-Uyghurchä lughät; English-Uighur Dictionary.* Ürümchi: Shinjang Khälq Näshriyati, 1988.

Sadvaqasov [Sadvakasov], G. *Iazyk uigurov Ferganskoi doliny.* [The Language of the Ferghana Valley Uyghurs.] 2 vols. Alma-Ata: "Nauka" Kazakhskoi SSR, 1970-1976.

Schwarz, Henry G. *An Uyghur-English dictionary.* Bellingham, Wash.: Western Washington University Press, 1992.

Sinjon, Danyel [St. John, Daniel]. *A Uighur-English Dictionary; Uyghurchä-Inglizchä lughät.*

Ürümchi: Shinjang Khälq Näshriyati, 1992.

Song, Zhengchun. "Multilingual families of the Tuvinian people in Xinjiang (Mongolia)." *International Journal of the Sociology of Language*, 97 (1992): 23-35.

Tenishev, Edgem R. *Uigurskie teksty.* [Uyghur Texts.] Moscow: Nauka, 1984.

— *Uigurskii dialektnyi slovar.* [Uyghur Dialect Dictionary.] Moscow: "Nauka", 1990.

Yaqub, Abliz, et al. *Shinjang Uighur Aptonom Rayonluq Millatlar Til-Yeziq Khizmiti Komiteti Lughat Bölümi. Uighur tilining izahliq lughiti.* 6 vols. Beijing: Millätlär Näshriyati, 1990-1999.

Zhao Xiangru and Reinhard F. Hahn. "The Ili Turk people and their language." *Central Asiatic Journal*, 33/3-4 (1989): 260-289.

XI) Studies of Literature and Literary History

The study of medieval Turkic literary history and Turkic linguistics are fairly advanced but authors from the last 500 years have attracted less international interest and are assigned to one or another national literature. This results in tendentious literary histories that attempt to strengthen or at least adjudicate the validity of, for example, Uyghur or Uzbek claims to particular authors. Only a few studies such as those of Ärshidinov and Friederich have begun to move beyond the cataloging, categorizing and historicizing modes of literary analysis to understand literature in its social contexts, and local scholars have also been reluctant to accept religious materials such as hagiographies within the nationalized literary traditions. The simple model of an evolving "national" literature has overwhelmed the possibility of describing literature in use. But the materials for more detailed study are rich: many relevant editions of manuscript *ghazal*

collections and *dastans* have been published in Alma-Ata, Tashkent, Kashgar, Ürümchi and Beijing, as well as in the journal *Bulaq*.

Ärshidinov, Batur. *Uyghur klassikliri ijadiyitigä dastan zhanri (XIX äsirning birinchi yerimi).* Alma-Ata: Nauka, 1988. [A study of the written *dastan* genre of Uyghur poetry during the first half of the nineteenth century, when popular rebellions became an important sources for *dastan* narratives.]

Friederich, Michael. *Die ughurische Literatur in Xinjiang 1956-1966.* Wiesbaden: Harrassowitz, 1997.

Ghochur, Vahtijan and Äsqär Husäyin. *Uyghur klassik ädibiyati tezisiliri.* Beijing, 1987. [A wide-ranging history of the authors and works that are now considered part of the Uyghur literary tradition, from the Uyghur Qaghanate through the Idiqut kingdom and the Qarakhanids, including Abu Nasr Muhammad Farabi and many Chaghatay authors, but excluding popular poets such as Mashrab and Huwaydâ who have been assigned to the Uzbeks.]

Jarring, Gunnar. *Some notes on eastern Turki (New Uighur) munazara literature.* Lund: C. W. K. Gleerup, 1981.

— *'The Thiefless City' and 'The Contest between Food and Throat.'* Scripta Minora 1989-1990:1. Lund: C. W. K. Gleerup, 1989.

— *Prints from Kashghar; the printing-office of the Swedish mission in eastern Turkestan.* Stockholm: Almqvist & Wiksell, 1991.

Kaidarov, A. T. *Razvitie sovremennogo Uigurskogo literaturnogo iazyka.* [The Development of the Contemporary Uyghur Literary Language.] Alma-Ata: 1969. [Soviet Uyghur version of the development of Uyghur literary poetry and prose.]

Khamraev, M. K. *Osnovy tiurskogo stikhoslozheniia; na materiale uigurskoi klassicheskoi i sovremennoi poezii.* [The Foundations of Turkic Versification; Based on the Materials of Uyghur Classical and Contemporary Poetry.] Alma-Ata: Izd-vo AN Kazakhskoi SSR, 1963.

Light, Nathan. "Kazakhs of the Tarbaghatai: Ethno-History Through a Novel." *The Turkish Studies Association Bulletin*, 17/2 (1993): 91-102. [Analysis of a novel about nomadic life from an ethnographic perspective.]

Mollaoudov, Savut. *Bilal Nazimning haiati va ijadi*. Alma-Ata: Qazaqstan SSR "Nauka" nashriati, 1976. [The life and works of the author Bilal Nazim who worked with N. Pantusov.]

—, and Gh. Sadvaqasov. *Uighur adabiatining qisqicha tarixi*. Alma-Ata: Qazaqstan SSR "Nauka" nashriati, 1983.

—. *XVIII äsir uighur poeziiasi (tätiqat va tekstlar)*. Alma-Ata: "Nauka" nashriati, 1990.

Naby, Eden. "Uighur literature: the antecedents." In: *Cultural Change and Continuity in Central Asia*. Shirin Akiner, ed. London: Kegan Paul, 1991, pp. 14-28.

Narynbaev, Aziz I. *Progressivnaya obshchestvenno-filosofskaya mysl' Uigurov vtoroi poloviny XIX v.* Frunze: Ilim, 1988. [Social philosophies of late 19th-century Uyghur authors in order to reclaim ancestors as progressive thinkers.]

Shahrani, M. Nazif. "Local Knowledge of Islam and Social Discourse in Afghanistan and Turkistan in the Modern Period." In: *Turko-Persia in Historical-Perspective*, Robert L. Canfield, ed. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, pp. 161-188. [Good description of literature in use by nomads from Eastern Turkistan.]

Sherip, Islamjan and Abdukerim Rakhman, eds. *Uyghur pälsäpä tarikhighä a'it mäsililär*. Kashgar: Qäshqär Uyghur Näshriyati, 1981. [Articles about the philosophical tradition expressed by Uyghur authors.]

Thwaites, Dilber. "Zunun Kadir's ambiguity; the dilemma of a Uyghur writer under Chinese rule." Unpublished Ph.D. dissertation. Australian National University, 2001.

Wei Cuiyi. "An Historical Survey of Modern Uyghur Writing since the 1950s in Xinjiang, China." *Central Asiatic Journal*, 37/3-4 (1993): 249-322.

XII) Performing Arts, Ethnomusicology, Folklore, Folk Art, Architecture and Material Culture

The study of Turkic, Mongol and Manchu folk traditions in Eastern Turkistan has a long history, and oral literature and music in particular have remained productive topics for research and publishing while religion has been more sensitive in China and the Soviet Union. Folk *qoshaq* and *dastan* songs have been published and analyzed in Russian and Uyghur, but there has been little comparative investigation of the widely circulated materials such as the romantic dastans and Nasirdin Äpändi (Hoca Nasreddin) tales. M. Alieva has written on the characteristics of oral folklore genres: *nakhsha*, *bäyt* and *qoshaq* (songs), *läpär* (humorous song and dance performances), *tepishmaq* (riddles), *maqal-tämsil* (proverbs, sayings), *chöchäk* (tale), *rivayät* (legend), *äpsanä* (myth), *lätipä* (humorous anecdotes), but despite the excellent work of Radlov, Pantusov, Katanov, Malov (see under linguistics), Jarring, Le Coq, and Reichl there has been little comparative or ethnographic work on narrative and song forms. In addition to items listed here many others Uyghur song and tale collections have been published in Xinjiang and Kazakstan, making the available material very rich.

International interest over the past 20 years has focused on the Uyghur muqam song tradition because of its importance as a symbol of Uyghur cultural identity and history and its relationship to *maqamat* traditions in other parts of Eurasia, with the work of Light, Trebinjac, Tsai and Zhou being the most important. Since the 1950s expanding and standardizing the muqam repertoire has been heavily supported in Xinjiang and Kazakstan in order to present muqams as the centerpieces of Uyghur traditional culture. Similarly, interest in Qirghiz, Mongol and Manchu/Sibe has focused on the

epic traditions, such as the famous *Manas* epic of Jusup Mamay which may be as long as 500,000 lines in its full extent. Other performing arts and material culture are being studied in some detail, with the best ethnographic work done by Dautcher and Harris.

Alakhunov, A. *Uighur Khaliq Qoshaqliri*. Alma-Ata: Nauka, 1977.

Alibakieva, Tamara. *Uigurskie istoricheskie pesni*. [Uyghur Historical Songs.] Moscow: Sovetskii kompozitor, 1986. [Songs and musical transcriptions.]

Alieva, Makhinur M. *Uighur khaliq chöchäkliri*. Alma-Ata: Zhazushy nashriati, 1969.

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Aratan, Ekrem Ural. *Kâshgar agzindan derlemeler*. Ankara: Ankara Üniversitesi Basımevi, 1965. [Oral materials from Kashgar.]

Baqi, Tokhti. *Uyghur tamaqliri*. Shinjang Khäiq Näshriyati, 1984. [Traditional Uyghur foods.]

Chao Gejin. *Qiannian juechang yingxiongge: Weilate Menggu shishichuan tongtian yesanji = The heroic songs of the past: fieldnotes on the Oirat Mongolian epic tradition*. Nanning: Guangxi renmin chubanshe, 2004.

Çubukçu, Bayhan and Söhret A. Oghuzoghlu. "Geleneksel Uygur Tibbinda Kullanilan Bitkisel Ilac Hammaddeleri." *Türk halk kültürü arastirmalari* 1994. Ankara: Kültür Bakanligi, 1996, p. 43-60. [Methods of Uyghur healing.]

Dautcher, Jay. "Folklore and Identity in a Uyghur Community in Xinjiang, China." Unpublished Ph.D. dissertation. University of California, Berkeley, 1999.

Du Yaxiong and Zhou Ji. *Sichou zhi lu de yinyue wenhua*. Beijing: Minzu chubanshe, 1997. [A study of Silk Road musical culture by two excellent ethnomusicologists.]

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- Harris, Rachel. "Music, Identity and Persuasion: ethnic minority music in Xinjiang, China." Unpublished Ph.D. dissertation. University of London, 1998.
- . "Cassettes, Bazaars and Saving the Nation: the Uyghur Music Industry in Xinjiang, China." In: *Global Goes Local: Popular Culture in Asia*. T. Craig & R. King, eds. Vancouver: University of British Columbia Press, 2001, pp. 265-83.
- . "Wang Luobin: 'Folksong King of the Northwest' or Song Thief? Copyright, representation and Chinese 'folksongs'." In: *Consuming China: approaches to cultural change in contemporary China*. Kevin Latham and Stuart Thompson, eds. Curzon Press, forthcoming. [Appears to be planned for late 2005.]
- , and Rahile Dawut. "Mazar Festivals of the Uyghurs: Music, Islam and the Chinese State." *Ethnomusicology Forum*, 11/1 (2002): 101-18.
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- . *Singing the village: music, memory and ritual among the Sibe of Xinjiang*. Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2005.
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- . "Die Geschichte von den Vierzig Leibern (Ḃilten). I. Ein türkischer Text aus Jarkend." *Mitteilungen des Seminars für Orientalische Sprachen*, 8 (1905): 25-38.
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- Jarring, Gunnar. *Materials to the knowledge of Eastern Turki; tales, poetry, proverbs, riddles, ethnological and historical texts from the southern parts of Eastern Turkestan, with translation and notes*. 4 vols. *Lunds universitets årsskrift*, N.F. 43/4, 44/7, and 47/3-4. Lund: C. W. K. Gleerup, 1946-1951. [1. Texts from Khotan and Yarkand. 2. Texts from Kashghar, Tashmalig and Kucha. 3. Folk-lore from Guma. 4. Ethnological and historical texts from Guma.]
- . *Matters of Ethnological Interest in Swedish Missionary Reports from Southern Sinkiang*. Lund: C. W. K. Gleerup, 1979.
- . *The Moen Collection of Eastern Turki (New Uighur) Proverbs and Popular Sayings*. Scripta Minora 1984-1985:1, Lund 1984.
- . *Garments from Top to Toe; Eastern Turki texts relating to articles of clothing*. Stockholm: Almqvist & Wiksell, 1992.
- . *Stimulants among the Turks of Eastern Turkestan: an Eastern Turki text edited with translation, notes and glossary*. Stockholm: Almqvist & Wiksell, 1993.
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XIII) Anthropology, Cultural Analysis, Ethnography, Ethnicity, Ethnogenesis

Ethnic identity and ethnogenesis in Xinjiang have been a central focus of study for many scholars. Cesaro, Clark, Gladney, Hoppe, Roberts, Rudelson, Smith, and Svanberg offer nuanced insights into the complexities of ethnicity, but Gladney's point that ethnic distinctions are not very important when Uyghurs move to Turkey should be extended to the situation in Xinjiang as well: ethnic identity is only contingently salient and much is missed by an exclusive focus on it. As with many of the literary studies above, ethnographers tend towards too much attention to ethnic differences. Ethnic identities are important modes of negotiating political and social organization and activities both on the interpersonal and on the level of state bureaucracy and public performances, but they offer only a partial perspective on social life. Life in Xinjiang involves more than deciphering the changing ways politics, culture, history, and rights are linked to ethnicity. Practices more strongly associated with gender, class, and religion—although these are also changing—are equally important, and here the works of Bellér-Hann and Hann are particularly valuable. Historical accounts of cultural practices can be found in the works on Chvyr,

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XIV) Religion: Islam, Khwāja Rule, Sufism, Shamanism

Religious practices and the history and politics of religion in the region now called Xinjiang offer many aspects and sources for study. Studies of religious practices were limited by PRC government policies until recently, but many earlier officials, ethnographers and explorers made detailed reports about religion. Most of the historical and ethnographic items included above mention religion, and the Islamic primary sources are particularly important for these topics as Islam became increasingly important in the social and political lives of Turkic speakers over the past 500 years. In addition to items listed below, the works of Bellér-Hann on healing practices, the historical studies by Fletcher and Hartmann, and the collections of folklore by Katanov, Pantusov, and Radlov are particularly rich sources for religious ideas and practices.

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XV) Ecology, Economics, Geography, Pastoralism

Economics and geography have been topics of interest to imperial powers involved Eastern Turkistan since the Manchu conquest in 1758, or even before if Miyawaki Junko is correct in seeing Junghar history as driven in part by a quest for economic control over the Tarim agricultural regions. The study of the cultural and ecological bases of pastoral nomadism has long

fascinated scholars of Eurasia, and motivated analysis of the ecological basis of political and military expansion, as in Owen Lattimore's *Inner Asian Frontiers of China* (N.Y., 1940). Many of the historical works listed above follow up these issues in more detail, as well as the studies on Qazaqs [Kazakhs] by Benson, Svanberg, Hoppe and Light.

Eastern Turkistan's trade ties with nearby regions and its participation in "Silk Road" trade more generally have been another focus of scholarly attention. Millward's article on the silk-horse trade and *Beyond the Pass* (listed in "world history" above) and Saguchi's article on Kokand trade provide excellent introductions. Fletcher's article in *Cambridge History of China* also discusses trade ties. The expedition reports and articles by Roberts, Toops and Wiemer in the volume edited by Starr listed above are also important discussions of trade and economics.

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XVI) Analyses of Social Policies, Politics, Strategic Issues and Current Events

Recent political analyses have moved somewhat beyond the collation and analysis of press reports that was the dominant mode for the study of Communist China from the 1950s through the 1980s. Now that fieldwork and archival research are more feasible, more sophisticated studies are being published, although analysis of news and propaganda reports continues. Becquelin, Bovingdon, Dwyer and Millward offer the best insights into present conditions. Most of the articles in the 1998 CEMOTI issue and in *Xinjiang: China's Muslim Borderland* (Starr, ed.) are also relevant here. Dillon's volume is a useful but uncritical analysis of Chinese studies on Islamic political movements.

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Bactrian Camels and Bactrian-Dromedary Hybrids

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If the Silk Road may be described as "the bridge between Eastern and Western cultures," then the Bactrian camel should rightfully be considered the principal means of locomotion across that bridge. Yet there is a great deal of misinformation concerning the Bactrian camel and its relatives, particularly in the ancient Near Eastern literature. This paper explores some of the problems surrounding *Camelus bactrianus* and the little-known hybrids of the Bactrian with the Arabian dromedary (*Camelus dromedarius*).

Zoologists nowadays tends to favor the idea that *Camelus bactrianus* and *dromedarius* are descendants of two different subspecies of *Camelus ferus* (Peters and von den Driesch 1997: 652), and modern research suggests that the original habitat of the wild, two-humped camel extended from the great bend of the Yellow River in northwestern China through Mongolia to central Kazakhstan (Schaller 1998: 154; Nowak 1999: 1078; Bannikov 1976: 399) generally at elevations of 1500-2000 m. above sea-level. Although some scholars have suggested the original habitat of *C. ferus* may have extended as far west as the Caspian Sea, this is unlikely. If this were true, we should expect to find *C. ferus* faunal remains at prehistoric and early historic sites around the Caspian, but this is not the case. Moreover, to suggest that the natural distribution areas of the wild two-humped camel extended so far to the west flies in the face of everything that is known about the physiology and environ-

mental adaptations of *C. bactrianus* (see below).

The survival of *C. ferus* in Inner Asia was long suspected but no firm evidence was available until N.M. Przewalski killed and described several specimens in 1873 (*Camelus ferus* Przewalski 1878 [?]). *C. ferus* has been described as "relatively small, lithe, and slender-legged, with very narrow feet and a body that looks laterally compressed" (Schaller 1998: 152).² *C. ferus* has "low, pointed, cone-shaped humps - usually about half the size of those of the domestic camel in fair condition" (Bannikov 1976: 398). Representations of camels in the rock art of Palaeolithic caves in eastern Mongolia, such as Chojt-Zenker Cave, show what are believed to be *C. ferus* (Peters and von den Driesch 1997: 653, 661).³ (Fig. 1) *C. ferus* were still hunted in the medieval era in the Khotan, Turfan, Tarim, Lob and Katak regions of Inner Asia, and in Mongolia (Roux 1959-60: 50-51), while 18th-century Chinese

Fig. 1. Pre-historic cave image of camel. Display in National Museum of Mongolian History, Ulaan Baatar.